

Effect of insecticides applied in the root zone on brown planthopper and green leafhopper. IRRI insectary, 1980.

Treatment (1.0 kg a.i./ha)	Mortality ^a (%)									
	Brown planthopper					Green leafhopper				
	1 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	20 DAT	1 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	20 DAT
Carbofuran 12 F	100 a	100 a	86 a	83 a	13 a	100a	100a	94a	83 a	86 a
UC54229 100% Tech.	76 b	48 b	8 b	43 b	1 b	99 a	88 a	71 b	66a	71 ab
UC SF-1 40 F	60 b	66 b	10 b	21 b	3 ab	99 a	95 a	53 b	75 a	64 b
RP32861 25 EC	10 c	9 c	4 b	1 c	1 b	3 b	6 b	8 c	1c	3 c
Control	10 c	6 c	4 b	9 bc	5 ab	1 b	4 b	1 c	10 bc	1 c

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT = days after treatment. Mortality readings were taken 48 hours after placing insects on plants.

rating to develop practical root-zone application methods but insecticides that are highly systemic and effective as a root-zone application are few.

Three coded compounds were compared with carbofuran in a greenhouse test to determine their activity when applied in the root-zone (see table).

UC54229 and UC SF-1 are carbamates and RP32861 is an oxadiazol. UC SF-1 is micronized carbaryl in an aqueous

solution. The insecticides were injected into the soil in porcelain pots with a syringe. Twenty brown planthoppers (*Nilaparvata lugens*) and 20 green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens*) female adults were placed on 35-day-old caged TN1 plants at 1, 5, 10, 15, and 20 days after treatment (DAT). Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging the insects.

Only carbofuran provided effective

control against the brown planthopper. UC54229 and UC SF-1 were effective against the green leafhopper. In previous tests, UC54229 and UC SF-1 applied as foliar sprays provided no control at 10 DAT. Increase in residual activity when applied in the root zone warrants further testing of UC54229 and UC SF-1 for field control of green leafhoppers and tungro virus. ■

Predators of rice bugs in southern Sri Lanka

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The rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* (F.) has been detected feeding on milky

grains in large numbers during the major cultivation season yala (April-July) in southern Sri Lanka. A survey of irrigated rice fields in Matara district revealed the occurrence of these predators of early nymphal instars: *Antiloclus nigripes* Burm. (Hemiptera:Pyrrhocoridae), *Canthecona robusta* Distant (Hemiptera:Pentatomidae), *Irantha* spp. (Hemiptera: Reduviidae), and *Cicindela*

sexpunctata F. (Coleoptera: Cicindelidae).

The predators were identified by the National Museum, Division of Entomology, Sri Lanka. Predator density was very low. Although rice bug density averaged 2-4/hill, only 0.5 (or fewer) predator/hill was found. That may explain the high incidence of rice bugs in the region. ■

Survey of natural enemies of paddy insect pests in Chhatisgarh (Madhya Pradesh), India

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No precise information on the occurrence of predatory and parasitic fauna on various insect pests of paddy has been available for integrated pest management planning. Therefore, surveys were undertaken on the paddy crop in Chhatisgarh region of Madhya Pradesh for 6 consecutive years, 1975-80 kharif season. Some species identified as parasites and predators of major paddy pests

Parasites and predators of paddy insect pests in Chhatisguh (M.P.), 1975-80.

Natural enemy	Host	Prevalence	Years of Occurrence
<i>Common</i>			
<i>Platygaster oryzae</i>	<i>Orseolia oryzae</i>	Moderate	1979-80
<i>Propicroscystus mirificus</i> (Girault)	"	High	1979-80
<i>Polygnotus</i> spp.	"	Trace	1975-80
<i>Proleptacis oryzae</i>	"	Trace	"
<i>Telenomus israeli</i>	"	Trace	"
<i>Neanastatus</i> spp.	"	Trace	"
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	High	"
<i>Gonatopus</i> spp.	<i>Nephotettix</i> spp.	Moderate	1978-80
	<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	High	1979-80
	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	Trace	1977
<i>Apanteles</i> spp.	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	Trace	1975-80
<i>Stenobracon</i> spp.	"	Trace	1975-80
<i>Uncommon</i>			
<i>Apalochrus fasciatus</i> (F)	Host not determined	High	1975-80
<i>Pheidole</i> spp.	"	Moderate	"
<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i> (Latreille)	"	High	"
Dragonflies	"	High	"
Damseflies	"	High	"

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of the region are listed in the table. Dr. N. C. Pant, director, British Museum, London; and Dr. A. D. Pawar, assistant director (Biological Control), Directorate of Plant Protection Quarantine & Storage, assisted in the identification. ■

Table continued

Natural enemy	Host	Prevalence	Years of occurrence
<i>Aphidius</i> spp.	"	High	"
<i>Selina westermanni</i> (Mots.)	"	High	"
Spiders	"	High	"
<i>Amphipsyche meridiana</i> Ulmer	"	High	1975-76

Leaffolder outbreak in Kohima District, Nagaland, India

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocis medinalis* Guenee was recorded as a minor pest in 1977 and 1978. But the pest caused heavy damage during the 1979 wet season (Jun-Nov), with infestations peaking in early September. Infestation

on IR8 leaves varied from 20% at higher altitudes (1,400 m mean sea level [MSL]) to 36% at lower altitudes (250 m MSL). Infestations seem to be increasing, up to 70% on IR8 and local variety Nagaland Special in 1981. ■

Gall midge incidence at Manipur, India

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A heavy incidence of gall midge was recorded during 1979-80 kharif in a few pockets of Manipur. To assess the extent of pest incidence, a field survey was conducted in six subdivisions when the crop reached the mid- to late-tillering stage. Fifty hills per variety per loukol (a group of fields) was the survey unit. Observations were recorded from four survey units per subdivision. Varieties planted varied among subdivisions. Percentage of silver shoots was calculated on the basis of actual number of silver shoots and number of tillers per

Gall midge infestation in 6 subdivisions of Manipur, India.

Rice variety	Silver shoots (%)						Mean
	Imphal West 1	Imphal West 11	Imphal East	Thoubal	Bishenour	Churachandpur	
Punshi	22.0	12.7	32.4	23.8	15.0	—	21.2
Phouoibi	26.7	14.2	26.0	38.3	16.9	—	22.4
IR24	43.6	10.8	29.3	23.3	19.4	12.7	23.3
Ratna	46.4	—	6.9	23.2	—	24.5	25.2
P.33	42.1	9.8	—	5.6	21.0	—	19.6
Moirangphou	—	17.7	9.6	4.9	3.9	9.5	9.1
Phourel	—	—	6.2	5.1	6.5	11.27	7.2
Mean	36.2	13.0	18.4	17.8	13.8	14.7	18.3
CD (P = 0.05)	3.17	5.25	4.33	6.03	5.11	2.82	

unit.

Gall midge incidence (see table) was highest in Imphal West I and lowest in Imphal West II. The lowest use of plant protection in Imphal West I perhaps accounted for the high incidence of the pest there. In Churachandpur, gall

midge incidence was low because the area planted to susceptible high yielding varieties was small. Ratna, IR24, Punshi, and Phouoibi were found to be more susceptible to the insect than local varieties Phourel and Moirangphou (see table). ■

Occurrence of rice stem borers and gall midges at Tirur, Chingleput District, India

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To determine the damage patterns of yellow stem borer and gall midge, two major pests of rice in Chingleput, the susceptible variety IR8 was planted in 40-m² plots every month from July 1978 to June 1979. Recommended agronomic practices were adopted. The crop was given no insecticide treatment.

Stem borer and gall midge infestations were assessed at 60 days after transplanting by recording the number

Rice stem borer and gall midge damage to IR8 at Tirur, India, 1978-79.